

Kinetics of the Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Isobutyrohydroxamic Acid

B. S. MANE and M. H. JAGDALE

Department of Chemistry,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur 416 004,
Maharashtra (India)

Manuscript received 14 October 1976; revised 1 February 1977; accepted 10 March, 1977

The kinetics of the hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid has been investigated in hydrochloric, perchloric and sulphuric acid over the range of 1 M to 8 M at 40° spectrophotometrically. The rate constant increases with an increase in acid concentration and attains optimum value in 4-6 M. Detailed kinetic study using concepts such as the ionic strength effect, activation parameters and kinetic order support a bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on the conjugate acid species of isobutyrohydroxamic acid. The variation of reaction rate with acid concentration can be better explained by a two parameter equation which takes into account an ionic strength effect and water activity raised to the second power.

THE hydrolysis of few hydroxamic acids¹⁻⁵ have been studied and it is concluded that it would appear logical to compare their hydrolysis with corresponding reaction of amides. Kinetic studies do indeed suggest that the mechanism of acid and base catalysed hydrolysis of benzohydroxamic acid and its derivatives^{2,5} resembles to that of amides.

Hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid has been studied⁴ in *p*-toluene sulphonic acid at 50.2°. But no detail path of the reaction has been studied in stronger aqueous mineral acids.

We have studied the catalytic effects and existence of maxima of the hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid in perchloric, hydrochloric and sulphuric acid. The experiments were carried out between the range 40°-55°. It has been found that the acid hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid proceed via the formation of the conjugate acid species.

Experimental :

The isobutyrohydroxamic acid was prepared from known procedure⁶ and recrystallized from ethyl acetate and had m.p. 118° (lit⁶. 118°-122°). The acids used were of analytical reagents quality. Their concentrations were determined by titration with standard alkali, sodium chloride used of Analar quality and all solutions were prepared in distilled water. Heavy water (99.4%) was obtained from BARC., Bombay.

Kinetic measurements were carried out at the temperature chosen maintained within ± 0.5 by withdrawing aliquots at proper time intervals. The decrease of hydroxamic acid was followed spectro-

metrically at 520 nm. using its reaction⁷ with ferric ion. As the extinction depends on pH, constant conditions were used giving maximum extinction i.e. pH 2.0 \pm 0.2 and 4.0 gms. FeCl₃·6H₂O per litre. Pseudo first order rate constants were obtained from the standard equation or graphically from the plot of log (Dt-D ∞) against time.

Results and Discussion

The rate of hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid was studied at its different concentrations at 40°. The reaction rate coefficient in isobutyrohydroxamic acid hydrolysis was found to be independent of its concentration (Table 1).

TABLE—1. EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF ISOBUTYROHYDROXAMIC ACID ON ITS HYDROLYSIS IN HYDROCHLORIC ACID AT 40°

Isobutyrohydroxamic Acid (M)	Hydrochloric Acid	k x 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹
0.012	1.0	4.7
0.010	1.0	4.8
0.008	1.0	4.8

Effect of Acid Concentration on Reaction Rate *k*

It has been observed that the reaction rate increases with increasing acid concentration, reaches a maximum and again decreases, as that of amide hydrolysis⁸. The rate maxima of the acid catalysed hydrolysis of benzohydroxamic acid its derivatives was observed^{2,5}. Results are interpreted by a reaction sequence starting with a rapid reversible

proton transfer to the substrate.

$R.CONHOH + H_3O^+ \rightleftharpoons RC(OH)NHOH + H_2O$
 The conjugate acid is formulated protonated oxygen atom, but the tautomer with the protonated nitrogen atom must be considered too. As the hydrolysis of amides⁹ proceed by two competitive reactions i.e. nucleophilic attack of the both forms protonated at oxygen and nitrogen we admit this possibility for the hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid too, the respective transition state being formulated as,

Here,

The reaction rate decreased at higher acidities (where the substrate is mainly present in its protonated form) caused by decreasing activity of the nucleophile (water molecules).

TABLE—2. EFFECT OF CONCENTRATIONS OF ACID ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF ISOBUTYROHYDROXAMIC ACID AT 40°

Acid (M)	HClO ₄ k x 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	HCl k x 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	H ₂ SO ₄ k x 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹
1.0	4.00	4.70 a	5.30
2.0	6.40	9.30	9.70
3.0	9.70	13.10	14.30
4.0	9.00	15.30	17.00
5.0	7.50	17.10	13.20
6.0	6.66	17.60 b	9.30
7.0	4.00	13.60	6.30
8.0	—	11.10	4.00

a = in 99.4% D₂O k x 10⁵ sec⁻¹ = 7.80
 b = in 99.4% D₂O k x 10⁵ sec⁻¹ = 20.00

Effect of Temperature :

The hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid is investigated at various temperatures, between the temperature range 40-55°. The activation parameter values for 1M hydrochloric acid catalyzed hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid are,

$\Delta E = 17.1 \text{ k cal/mole,}$
 $\Delta H^\ddagger = 16.4 \text{ k cal/mole.}$
 $\Delta S^\ddagger = -25.8 \text{ e.u.}$
 $A = 4.1 \times 10^7 \text{ sec}^{-1}$

These values are in favour [of bimolecular mechanism.

Effect of Ionic Strength :

The rate coefficients were determined at different

acidities by keeping the ionic strength constant with hydrochloric acid sodium chloride (Table 3).

TABLE—3. EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTHS ON REACTION RATE OF HYDROLYSIS OF ISOBUTYROHYDROXAMIC ACID AT 40°

Sr. No.	HCl (M)	NaCl (M)	Ionic Strength (μ)	k x 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	k _{H⁺} x 10 ⁵ M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1	1.0	0.0	1.0	4.70	4.64
2	0.75	0.25	1.0	3.60	
3	0.50	0.50	1.0	2.60	
4	0.25	0.75	1.0	1.40	
5	2.0	0.0	2.0	9.30	5.00
6	1.5	0.5	2.0	7.60	
7	1.0	1.0	2.0	5.10	
8	0.5	1.5	2.0	2.80	
9	3.0	0.0	3.0	13.50	5.28
10	2.5	0.5	3.0	12.60	
11	2.0	1.0	3.0	10.20	
12	1.0	2.0	3.0	5.40	

From the values of the rate coefficients at different acidities at a particular ionic strength, the reaction can be represented by the equation,

$k = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \quad \dots (1)$

where k and k_{H⁺} are the observed and specific rate constants. It is found that the values of specific rate k_{H⁺} increased with increase in ionic strength. This leads to the conclusion that reaction exhibits a positive ionic strength effect. It is observed from the plots, representing rate coefficients at different acidities pass through origin, leading to inform that the reaction due to neutral species is absent. The rate data may be represented by a modified form of the Bronsted-Bjerrum equation¹⁰,

$k = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \cdot e^{b\mu} (a_{H_2O})^n \quad \dots (2)$

where a_{H₂O} is activity of water¹¹, 'n' is the number of water molecules and 'μ' the ionic strength.

The values of k_{H⁺} are plotted against ionic strength. From the plot, values of k_{H₀⁺} and b are calculated. k_{H₀⁺} is the intercept of zero ionic strength and 'b' is the slope of the line. The value of k_{H₀⁺} is 4.365 x 10⁵ M⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and the value of slope 'b' is 0.031. The theoretical values of rate coefficient at different acidities were calculated using n=2 in equation 2. These values are found to be in close agreement with the experimental values (Table 4).

TABLE—4. COMPARISON OF OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATES FOR THE HYDROCHLORIC ACID CATALYZED HYDROLYSIS OF ISOBUTYROHYDROXAMIC ACID AT 40°

HCl (M)	Expt. k x 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	Calcd. k x 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	H ₂ O
1.0	0.47	0.430	0.96
2.0	0.93	0.834	0.91
3.0	1.25	1.171	0.85
4.0	1.53	1.413	0.78
5.0	1.71	1.527	0.70
6.0	1.76	1.544	0.62
7.0	1.55	1.408	0.53
8.0	1.36	1.200	0.44

The Kinetic solvent isotope effect :

The values of the kinetic solvent isotope effect $k(D_2O/H_2O)$ for the hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid in HCl 1.0 M and HCl 6.0 M at 40° are 1.70 and 1.14 respectively suggests that protonation occurs by a rapid preequilibrium proton transfer which finally undergo bimolecular attack of water leading to the products.

The conjugate acid is written here as the oxygen protonated form.

Mechanism of Hydrolysis :

After the initial pre-equilibrium proton transfer the decomposition of the conjugate acid species would occur in principle by either unimolecular (A_1) or a bimolecular (A_2) mechanism. Information about the mechanism of the rate limiting step can be obtained from the dependence on acidity of the rates of hydrolysis.

Bunnett and Olsen¹² suggested that the slopes (ϕ) of the plot of $\log k + H_0$ against $H_0 + \log (H)^+$ can be used as a criterion of mechanism. Three classes of reaction were classified in terms of the role of water in the rate limiting step.

- (i) $\phi < 0.0$ water not involved.
- (ii) $\phi = 0.22$ to 0.58 water involved as a nucleophile.
- (iii) $\phi > 0.58$ water involved as a proton transfer.

The observed value of ϕ is 1.25 for isobutyrohydroxamic acid hydrolysis. Therefore, the third category, implying that water has some additional role in the rate limiting step as well as that of nucleophile.

Bunton et al⁹. have suggested that for (A_1)

reactions the catalytic effects of added acids lies in the order,

$HClO_4 > HCl \sim H_2SO_4$ while for (A_2) reactions order is reversed. On this basis the relative effects of added acids on the hydrolysis of isobutyrohydroxamic acid provide further support for (A_2) mechanism.

Like the hydrolysis of amides this presumably involves bimolecular attack of the water molecule on the conjugate acid.

Acknowledgements

One of the authors (B.S.M.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship. The authors are indebted to Prof. Kenneth, A. Connors, University of Wisconsin, Madison (U.S.A.) for valuable discussions.

References :

1. D. C. BRENDT and R. L. FULLAR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 3312.
2. A. J. BUGLASS and H. HUDSON and J. G. TILLET, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1971, 123.
3. J. W. MUNSON and K. A. CONNORS. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 24, 1979.
4. D. C. BRENDT and J. K. SHARP, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1973, 38, 396.
5. A. AHMAD, J. SOCHA and M. VECERA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1974, 39, 3293-3303.
6. W. N. FISHBEIN; J. DALY and C. L. STREETER, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1969, 28, (1-3), 13-24.
7. G.M. STEINBERG and R. SWIDLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 2362.
8. M. M. MHALA and M. H. JAGDALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 147.
9. C. A. BUNTON, C. O'CONNOR and T.A. TURNEY, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1967, 1835.
10. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNNOLD. "Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions". (JOHN WILEY and SONS, Inc. New York and London), 1963, p. 286.
11. F. A. LONG and W. F. MCDEVIT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 51, 119.
12. J. F. BUNNETT and F. P. OLSEN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, 44, 1895 & 1917.